

Document Analysis as a Qualitative Research Method

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Abstract. *In qualitative research, the function of documents as a data source is explored in this paper, as well as the application of the document analysis technique to actual research contexts. The paper is a nuts-and-bolts paper, aimed at research novices. It describes the nature and forms of documents, outlines the benefits and drawbacks of document analysis, and provides concrete examples of how documents can be used in the research process. The application of document analysis to a grounded theory research is shown.*

Keywords: *Content analysis, documents, grounded theory, thematic analysis, triangulation.*

In qualitative research forms many years, organizational and institutional papers have been a staple. The number of research reports and journal papers that include document analysis as part of the methodology has increased in recent years. The insufficient detail in most journals reviewed by researchers has been particularly evident in the study of the procedure followed and the results of the documents' analyses. moreover, there is some evidence that document analysis hasn't been used effectively in qualitative research. The paper, which is primarily written for research novices, describes the nature and forms of documents, highlights the strengths and weaknesses of document analysis, and provides concrete examples of how documents are used in the research process. Document analysis is included in this book's fundamental aim to broaden readers' knowledge and understanding of document analysis as a quantitative research technique with the intention of enhancing its effectiveness. Analysis of documents defined a document analysis is a systematic method for reviewing or evaluating documents, both printed and electronic. Document analysis, like other analytical techniques used in qualitative research, requires that data be examined and understood in order to find meaning, gain insight, and develop empirical knowledge. Documents contain text (words) and photographs that have been recorded without the intervention of a researcher. Other mute or trace evidence, such

as cultural items, are not included in this discussion. atkinson and coffey refer to documents as "social facts" that are produced, shared, and used in a socially structured manner.

Documents that can be used for systematic assessment as part of a study receive various forms. Guides; Background Papers; Books and Brochures; Diaries and Magazines; Event Programs; Letters and Memorandum; Maps and Graphics; Maps and Graphics; Newspapers; Newspapers; Press Publications, Program offers, application forms and summary; Radio and television program scenarios;;Data, there is no doubt that the previous studies require the researcher to rely on the identification and interpretation of data instead of being a foundation for analysis. Analytical procedures, finding, selection, evaluation (interpretation) requires a visual signal. Data in Belge Analysis, Later Big themes, Categories and Content Analysis - Examples of data arranged as examples through exercises, excerpts or all passages.

The reason for analytical analysis of documents analysis is often used in the combination of a triangle methodologies in combination of combinations. It is worthwhile that a quality test will draw these sources of evidence and use the use of various sources of data and methods that adds to the control of sources, such as participants or participants. Researcher tries to confuse the evidence of trust "that breeds, researchers can reproduce discoveries during data set, so reducing the potential sides of prejudice in one study. Researchers researchers find a single method, sole source or single study that is mixed and qualitative and qualitative and qualitative and qualitative and qualitative (qualitative and qualitative) analysis of research analysis. Basic data) and document reviews (as primary) and document reviews). Document reviews for identifying agencies that support school improvement programs, they were developed. that they contribute to the image of general support agencies, while others focused on teaching and technologies engaged in technology, goals, goals, goals, goals, enrollment and proper content. Leadership or Snowman's skills were also determined by inspection of program documents

Specific use of documents can take into account the specific functions of a research work. Turn new interviews in poor communities of families, it has shown long-term ethnographic use of families. The research of the method can work. He helped to create new and participants in community activities. Documents offer additional research and approaches can be valuable applications of knowledge. Politics and self-assessment of school curricula was analyzed in an interview written by university documents and self-esteem of university policy. In the study of technological teachers, Connell, Lynch, and warnings, the document is shared as an organization. The analysis

of the document is used to form other sources, such as semi -structured conversations and thematic surveillance. In some case, when multi -stake is available, the researcher may compare changes to identifyChanges. Project changes can be displayed, for example, significant development in the project. To get a clear picture of how an organization or a program performed over time, the researcher may also look at periodic and final reports (where available). documents can also be used to verify findings or confirm data from other sources. Sociologists, in particular, use document analysis to verify their conclusions. If the forensic evidence is contradictory rather than corroboratory, the researcher is likely to continue investigating. Readers of the research paper have a higher confidence in the conclusions' trustworthiness when there is a convergence of data from different sources.

Advantages and limitations of document analysis document analysis has both advantages and limitations in comparison to other quantitative research methods. Let us first look at the disadvantages.

- efficient method: document analysis is less time-consuming and therefore more cost-effective than other research methods. It requires dataselection rather than datacollection.
- availability:many documents are in the public domain, especially since the advent of the internet, and are therefore unobtainable without the authors' permission. Documentation is therefore an attractive option for quantitative researchers. Findingpublic records is only limited by one's imagination and industriousness, merriam said. Keep in mind that if a public event occurred, there is a good chance that there is some official record of it.
- cost-effectiveness:documentation is less expensive than other research methods and is often the method of choice when collecting new data is impossible. The data (contained in papers) have already been collected; it is now time to analyze the content and quality of the documents.
- lack of obtrusiveness and reactivity:documents are both "unobtrusive" and "non-reactive," implying that they are unaffected by the research process. Therefore, document analysis addresses the shortcomings inherent in other qualitative research techniques. For example, an event can occur differently because it is being observed. In using documents for research purposes, reflexivity is usually not an issue. it requires an awareness of the researcher's contribution to the construction of meanings attached to social interactions as well as an acknowledgement of the researcher's influence.
- stability: documents are stable as a side effect of being non-reactive. The investigator's presence does not alter the study's conclusions. Documents, on the other hand, are suitable for repeated reading.
- exactness:the inclusion of precise names, references, and events makes documents useful in the analysis process.
- coverage:documents have a

broad range of coverage; they cover a long period of time, many events, and many locations.

Using documents in a grounded theory research paper the use of documents was integral to my grounded theory research of social funds. A social fund is both an intervention and the organization that manages it. It is used to address poverty-related challenges in the form of financial contributions. The social fund is a nonprofit organization that provides grants to small-scale development initiatives that are identified, planned, and implemented by the community. The social fund is a national government antipoverty initiative in Jamaica, where I did fieldwork for the report. The Jamaica Social Investment Fund supports community-based initiatives that restore and expand social and economic infrastructure, improve social services, and strengthen local governments. Local sponsors are community-based organizations, non-governmental organizations, and local governments. My research used a multimethod approach, which included semistructured interviews, non-participant observation, and document analysis. Although most grounded theory studies draw their inspiration from interviews and observations, complete investigations can be conducted with only papers. Pandit conducted one such study, using existing literature and records to create two case-study databases from which a grounded theory of corporate turnaround was drawn. The papers included articles in journals, trade journals, business journals, government journals, broker reviews, annual company reports, and press releases. The Pandit study was influenced by Turner's use of similar data in the quantitative analysis of organizational behavior, which included documentary sources that were "treated like sets of field notes." At the first paragraph of the book, an analysis and category selection was started, and a conceptual framework was developed to address the aspects that were perceived to be of interest to each paragraph. In my research, it was vital that the voices and viewpoints of ordinary people be heard. I thought it was the most possible that existing papers would serve as a reservoir or conduit for those voices and viewpoints. I used interviews as my primary data collection method for the past thirty-four years. At eight rural and urban sites where subprojects had been implemented, thirty-four respondents were interviewed individually. Additional data and clarification of specific topics were provided by ten key informants. As a way to figure out what was being done, when, and by whom was monitored, a series of community conditions and processes was included. It gave me a broader and deeper appreciation of how a social fund-supported subproject can impact community life in general and poverty in particular. During the same period as the interviews were conducted, field observation was conducted.

Document Analysis was an additional procedure to collect the Trian's seizure and building theory. Glazer and Stropas drew attention to the usefulness of the documents for the construction of the theory process, which begging the comparative analysis of the fantastic spectrum for a few months. I saw the document, placed them into the context and coded them for analysis. Social fund's policies and projects, meetings, letters, bulletins, annual special reports and 26 newspaper articles related to drug documents. Several documents have been made on the current research sites. Reports about protocols and meetings, some of them had notes and files containing newspaper clippings, images, letters, cards, cards and similar documents. Mostly interviews were forwarded to these documents, did not give me. With flour statistics, the brochure on the financial program, the anecdote data about the effect of the program along with the secondary school letter and the text of the Aral community that started the sub -project. These documents were the rich sources of Data.

Summary and conclusions of understanding the analysis of the document are essential that a qualitative research method notices and has determined the advantages and limits of this method .Thearticle has been interviewed by the systematic review of Document. To study the documents. It is a low cost of the minimum empirical data from the point of view and observation, which may be determined by the authenticity and utility of specific documents, by researchers in the context of each document and the latests of Wetxes. Subjective They should create the analysis process and strict and transparent. Qualitative requests are less.

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